

GERKON RELAY IS FIXED WITH NMP 69 M IN RAILWAY STATIONS

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Annotation: In this article, what is a reed relay and nmp 69. How it works, in what areas this technology is currently used and its effectiveness. The functions of nmp 69 relays are explained in detail based on gerkon relays technology.

Key words: nmp 69, reed relay, electromagnetic field, features and characteristics.

Introduction In modern production technologies, reed relays are used in all market segments, including test and measurement equipment, medical electronics, telecommunications equipment, automation, security systems, and others. Consumption is growing, and the global production of reed relays cannot meet the growing demand for them. Being hermetically sealed, they can be used in almost any environmental conditions. Very simple in their design, they combine a variety of production technologies. A critical indicator of quality and reliability is tightness at the point of contact between the glass of the housing and the metal of the contact terminal. These materials must have exactly the same temperature coefficient of linear expansion. Otherwise, cracks and poor tightness of the flask may occur. Regardless of the sputtering or electroplating technology, the process of applying contact materials (usually rhodium or ruthenium) requires high precision and special cleanliness of the production facilities, similar in requirements to semiconductor production. Similar to the production of semiconductors, any foreign particles present during production will result in increased losses, quality and reliability of the products. external magnetic field . Issues such as the automation of transportation process control systems in the world, the introduction of systems implemented on the basis of microprocessor technologies in the continuous control of the state of train traffic control devices, the improvement of methods and technologies of control are taking one of the leading places. Therefore, in the process of ensuring security, it is necessary to introduce into practice diagnostic systems that increase the operational reliability of automation and telemechanics devices at railway stations, which are implemented on the basis of microelectronics technologies. In developed countries of the world, such as the United States, Germany, Japan,

England, China and Spain, it is important to design and create railway automation and telemechanics systems, to ensure their stability, reliability and self-control, as well as to develop sophisticated microprocessor systems that give the necessary information about their technical condition.

In this article, research on the implementation of NPM-69 block with the help of gerkon relay is carried out. The functional function of this block is to control and control the condition of the railway traffic lights on the road site, which are located at the entrance to the train and manyovr traffic lights. Let's consider the Compatibility scheme of the NPM-69 block (picture 1). The fourth scheme of the (BRRC) dialing group is the compliance scheme (SCH), which checks whether the steering rails are in the correct position and their actual position after the arrows are held.

figure.1 Gerkon relay install instead of OP and PP relay with PVG in the NMP 69 block

Figure. 1 can be seen from the picture, when the contacts of the OP Relay are in a current state, the Manba current goes to the PP relay through the NKN contacts, if the contacts of the PP Relay are in a current state, the train confirms that the traffic light relay is in a current state. Or the contacts of the PP relay in the non-toxic state confirm that the relay of the magnifying glass passes through the contacts of the KN relay in a non-toxic state. If the contacts of the OP relay sine are in a non-toxic state, then the Manba current through the contacts of the

DESIGN, TYPES AND PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION

The design of the reed relay is simple. The element is based on an electromagnetic coil, on top of which there is a protective shield that protects the contact group from moisture, oxidation, dust and magnetic fields. In a sealed glass tubular case, in a vacuum or argon environment, there are two flexible ferromagnetic conductors with flat metal contacts made of permalloy coated with precious metals with high conductivity (silver and platinum group metals). Parts are produced by stamping, and connections are made by welding or soldering. The entire structure can be enclosed in a casing.

Figure 3. Reed relay device

The principle of operation of a reed relay is based on the interaction of forces arising between magnetic bodies. When the contact cores are exposed to a magnetic field, the contacts inside the glass cylinder are opened or closed. Gaps make it much easier for the field to pass between the elements of the device. In this way, the cores cope with the functions of a conductive element, a spring and a part that responds to a magnetic field, the source of which, as a rule, is an electric or permanent magnet.

Figure 4. Reed switches are divided into several groups according to the type of contact used:

High-density matrix relays

Our high-density reed matrix relays have been designed specifically for large and densely packed switching arrays.

Switch matrices are commonly used in functional PCB test systems. Internal magnetic shielding eliminates the effects of magnetic coupling between reed relays mounted very close together.

The CRF series is our smallest and most versatile tool-grade reed relay series. What's more, the CRF can transmit radio signals from DC to 7GHz. As well as fast digital pulses with a distortion rate of <20 picoseconds in an environment with an impedance of 50 ohms. In addition, the CRF series is our lowest profile reed relay with a height of only 3.6mm. Low displacement thermal stress. In fact, less than 1 μ V. Finally, the CRF series can operate reliably in a wide range of temperatures. First of all, this series of relays will perform billions of high-speed signal switching operations in a cost-effective way. Series Coil Voltage, (V) Coil Resistance (Ω) Contact Type Max. Power (W)

HF 5V, 12V, 24V 250 – 1000 1A (N.O.), 1B (N.O.) 25

MRE – High Frequency 5V, 6V, 12V, 24V 70 – 2000 1-2A (N.O.), 1E (Latching)

O. – Normally open

C. – Normally Closed

switchable or combined (one group actuates for opening, the other for closing).

Working Principle of a Reed Relay

Depending on the design, a distinction is made between dry (a cone with an inert gas or vacuum) and wet (the presence of mercury at the point of contact of the cores) varieties. A drop of mercury eliminates the rattling of the ferromagnetic cores.

The operation of a reed relay largely depends on the materials from which it is made. Four groups of magnets are used in the production of reed relays: neodymium plants are characterized by the highest coercivity and residual magnetization, but do not tolerate operation in environments with a high oxygen

content; ferrite magnets are very resistant to corrosion and the most affordable, but at the same time brittle magnets;

Samarium – have excellent thermal stability and resistance to demagnetization, but are distinguished by a high price and even greater brittleness than ferrite analogues;

Made of alnico alloy (aluminum, nickel, cobalt) – have better heat resistance and a relatively affordable price, but are endowed with low coercivity.

PROS AND CONS OF REED RELAYS

Among the advantages of the components: complete sealing of the contact group;

Significant electrical strength of the gap between the contact efficiency of functioning; compact, light weight and simple design; galvanic isolation of circuits;

functionality and lack of power requirements;

Efficient operation in different temperature environments (-60 to +120 °C).

The breakdown voltage of reed relays can reach several tens of kilovolts. The service life of such products can reach up to 4-5 billion actuations. High reliability is one of the main reasons for the wide range of reed switches.

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